

Identification of spatial patterns in European territories based on the assessment of renewable energy potential to support the 2030 Energy Strategy

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Abstract

1 The study presents an effort to classify the territories of a specific area, according to similarities in
2 the estimated potential of their renewable sources, considering also their economic and sociodemographic
3 structure and their geographic features. Specifically, the paper focuses on the area of the EU28 and uses
4 as basis for the analysis data estimating the potential of renewable energy sources, collected and elaborated
5 in the framework of the project HotMaps (Horizon 2020). The method used to group the territorial units
6 is cluster analysis, and specifically the k-means algorithm. The data present some interesting patterns and
7 the territories of EU28 at NUTS3 level are classified into 17 clusters. The analysis shows the presence
8 of heterogeneity within national borders and inside the macro regions target of specific EU programmes,
9 specifically the Adriatic-Ionian region, the Alpine region, the Baltic Sea region and the Danube region.
10 The results of this research are meant to be used by European policy makers in developing more focused
11 transnational renewable energy policies and strategies.

Keywords: Renewable energy sources; Energy planning; Energy policy; EU28

12 1. Introduction

13 Energy production and use represent a large share of greenhouse gas emissions responsible for global
14 warming and climate change. Replacing fossil fuels with renewable sources of energy provides the oppor-
15 tunity to tackle these phenomena by limiting the increase of global temperature. In 2014, the European
16 Council renewed its commitment to the energy transition through the 2030 Energy Strategy, which, among
17 other goals, aims at reaching a target of 27% for the share of renewables in energy consumption within 2030
18 [1].

19

20 EU leaders have been putting in place a structured framework of policies and guidelines encouraging
21 renewable energy production in order to reach the ambitious goals of the 2030 Energy Strategy [2, 3].

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22 EU programmes and policies are often put in place at national level or within the boundaries of macro-
23 regions: however these areas often comprise very diverse territories responding to energy transition policies
24 in different ways. Reiche and Bechberger [4] investigated the differences in energy policies, planning cultures
25 and the main instruments for the promotion of renewable energies used in individual EU countries. They
26 summarized the key success conditions for the promotion of renewable energies and underlined as some
27 Member States are more successful in promoting renewable energies than others even when using similar
28 promotion instruments.

29 At the same time, the increase in renewable energy production challenges scientists and researchers to
30 deal with the assessment of natural resource availability in European territories. In the literature, several
31 works [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11] deeply investigated renewable energy potential in the EU. Some studies [6, 11]
32 deal with raster data about energy potential at high spatial resolution, others [5, 7, 8, 9] are assessing the
33 energy potential at country level. Reviewing these works, one can see how the definition and meaning of
34 energy potential changes from a theoretical concept (i.e accounting only for physical laws) to a more tangible
35 one, accounting also for a sustainable use of energy sources [5, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16].

36
37 Although the energy potential assessment at European level has been widely investigated, few examples
38 in the literature focus on the identification of energy-related spatial patterns enhancing the effectiveness of
39 energy policies.

40 Increasing the effectiveness of energy policies can be supported by identifying and understanding different
41 territorial aspects within the same geographic or administrative area. One of the aim of the ESPON ECGT,
42 an European Grouping on Territorial Cooperation, is to inspire policy making with territorial evidence.
43 The 2005 ESPON "Regional Classification of Europe" project aimed at providing policy makers information
44 on territorial structures in Europe through clusterization of municipalities based on socio-economic, geo-
45 ecological and agricultural data [17]. Metzger et al. [18] used PCA (Principal Component Analysis) and
46 cluster analysis based on geomorphological variables to obtain a "statistical stratification of the European
47 environment". Cluster analysis based on economic variables has been used by Monfort et al. [19] to test the
48 presence of real convergence, "the process whereby the GDP per capita levels of lower-income economies
49 catch up with those of higher-income economies on a durable basis" [20], in the EU. Pecher et al. [17] tried
50 to come out with a "regional typology" of the Alpine Space, by using hierarchical cluster analysis based
51 on 26 "spatial-pattern indicators" to classify the municipalities of the area. Though being thorough, this
52 study considers exclusively geographic, topographic and landscape-related indicators thus its result is a
53 classification of the territories in these terms.

54 What is missing is a spatial analysis of energy potential indicators in order to identify the heterogeneities
55 within national borders and macro-regions and to investigate the presence of patterns and cross-borders
56 similarities.

57 The aim of this work is to propose a classification of EU28 territories based on energy potential indicators
58 and to identify clusters by means of a k-means algorithm. The evidence of energy-potential spatial patterns
59 can support policy makers in defining plans and strategies for renewable energy production.

60
61 The first challenge arises when considering the heterogeneity of energy potential indicators. In the liter-
62 ature, authors mainly work with data having different spatial resolution for each energy source. Not much
63 effort has been made towards leveling out the resolutions and analyze the data for all energy sources at the
64 same administrative level.

65
66 In order to perform a classification of territories, the first step was to find an unambiguous territorial
67 unit. Said territorial unit needs to fulfill two basic requirements:

- 68 • reliable data for the unit should be available or at least easily computable;
- 69 • the unit should be well known in the field of application and usable by the recipients of the results of
70 the analysis: policy makers, advisors and other stakeholders from the public and private sector must
71 be able to grasp the administrative boundaries of the territorial unit in question and easily retrieve its
72 energy policy framework.

73 The Classification of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS) is a "hierarchical system for dividing up
74 the economic territory of the EU" [21]. According to this system, countries are divided according to their
75 administrative partitions and the classification is structured in four levels

- 76 • NUTS0 is the less aggregated level, representing the country
- 77 • NUTS1 usually represent states or macro-regions
- 78 • NUTS2 typically represent regions
- 79 • NUTS3 is the most aggregated level of administrative subdivision and depending on the country can
80 indicate provinces (Italy, Spain), counties (Hungary, Croatia, Lithuania), districts or metropolitan
81 areas (Germany, UK) and other types of administrative micro-regions.

82 The territorial unit chosen for this study is NUTS3, the most aggregated thus potentially the one showing
83 most accurate results. This approach presents some issues. First, the division at NUTS3 level draws the
84 administrative subdivision of the territories differently depending on the country. Due to this fact, NUTS3
85 territories can be very diverse: for instance, in terms of surface area, the smallest NUTS3 unit, the city of
86 Melilla in Spain, comprises an area of 13 km², while the biggest unit, the county of Norrbotten in Sweden,
87 comprises an area of 105.205 km². Secondly, energy policies are not always implemented at NUTS3 level,

88 but rather at less aggregated levels. Nevertheless the NUTS3 division remains the most reliable when it
89 comes to data availability with the higher spatial resolution. Furthermore, EU policy makers have been
90 pushing forward with the collection of data at NUTS3 level, especially for energy related projects (ESPON
91 ECGT and HOTMAPS [22]) thus data at level NUTS3 can be found in official databases or, when present
92 at less aggregated levels, they can be easily re-elaborated. As for the second requirement, the administrative
93 borders of NUTS3 territorial units should be well-known in urban and regional energy planning: policy
94 makers are expected to be familiar with this classification and if not, to quickly grasp its concept and
95 context.

96 Being the aim of the study the investigation of possible patterns in the distribution of renewable energy
97 potential across a territory, the choice of indicators at NUTS3 level in this analysis is based on their rele-
98 vance in the study area and on the availability of data for the chosen territorial unit.

99
100 A second challenge is the different definition of energy potential in existing datasets. While a comparison
101 among potentials from different energy sources is an issue, using energy potential data as variables in a cluster
102 analysis partially solves this problem. However, an effort has to be made in order to have similar concepts of
103 potential for all energy sources since introducing specific constraints in the definition could lead to different
104 spatial distributions of data.

105 The data were mainly collected from four main sources: the Eurostat database [23], the Copernicus Land
106 Monitoring Service [24], several European projects (cited in 2.1 according to the renewable source for which
107 data were collected) and finally elaborations carried out by the authors within the HotMaps Horizon2020
108 project according to the methodology reported in section 2.1. With the aim of painting a more complete
109 picture of the territorial units, not only from an energy perspective, some indicators relative to geographic
110 features and the economic and sociodemographic structure were included in the analysis; they are presented
111 in section 2.3.

112 The cluster methodology is presented in section 3. Finally, the classification resulting from the analysis
113 is presented and discussed in section 4 with the help of GIS (Geographic Information System) tools, which
114 allow the spatial visualization of the data.

115 2. Renewable energy potential in Europe

116 2.1. Review of main energy potential indicators at European level

117 Resch et al. [14] defined the global energy potential for biomass, geothermal, hydro-power, ocean, solar
118 and wind energy. At European scale, several studies aimed at assessing the energy potential of these sources.
119 Based on the literature and ongoing EU financed energy projects, we selected some of the renewable sources

120 proposed by Resch et al. [14] and we introduced other energy-potential indicators that are becoming relevant
121 for the European Energy Strategy.

122 Paish [25] highlighted as most of the hydro-power potential in Europe has been already exploited by
123 dams and reservoir plants. Besides, the European Water Frame Directive [26] is willing to preserve the
124 water quality and pursue a sustainable river basin management. For these reasons, we did not include the
125 energy potential from hydro-power in our analysis.

126 Similarly, we excluded the energy potential from geothermal and aerothermal heat pump systems. In
127 fact, this potential is strictly correlated with the building design and technology and these systems currently
128 use external power coming from the national energy mix. Though recognizing the role these technologies
129 could play in covering the EU heat demand [27], they were not included in the study given the aim of
130 dealing more with the energy resource availability than on the technology aspects. Instead, we included the
131 energy potential of waste water treatment plants: Hepbasli et al. [28] highlights how waste water can be
132 very suitable for energy extraction. The potential of this energy source is less dependent on the building
133 design and it can be calculated at district level. Specifically, waste water treatment plants could be divided
134 in suitable or not suitable for energy production purposes based on their capacity and proximity to urban
135 areas [29]. Once identified the suitable plants, their energy potential was estimated at NUTS3 level in the
136 frame of the Horizon2020 HotMaps project [22].

137 Regarding ocean wave potential, Magagna and Uihlein [7] analyzed status and future perspective in
138 Europe. However, due to the difficulty with finding an indicator for this energy potential at NUTS3 level,
139 since strictly connected to the ocean area measured only at national level, this source was excluded from
140 the study.

141 Data on the potential of agricultural and forest biomass and livestock effluents were collected in the
142 framework of the Biomass Policies project by Elbersen et al. [30]. The project analyzed data from several
143 biomass sources also considering those cultivated purposely for biofuel production (energy crops). Energy
144 crops were excluded from this study due to the debated environmental impacts in terms of land use change
145 [31], water resources depletion and biodiversity losses [32, 33]. In this work, we selected agricultural residues
146 considered suitable for energy production from those included in the report according to two sustainability
147 criteria [30]: from the available biomass from crop residues we subtracted:

- 148 • the biomass to be left on the field for soil conservation
- 149 • the biomass destined to conventional competing uses (feedstock production, livestock bedding, other
150 agricultural and agro-industrial processes)

151 Agricultural residues considered in the study are summarized in table 1. The livestock effluents considered
152 for the estimation of energy potential comprise solid and liquid manure from cattle, pigs and poultry.

Crop	Production process	Residue
Cereals (excl. maize and rice)	Cereal production	Straw
Maize	Maize production	Stover
Oilseed rape and sunflower	Oil production	Stubble
Sugar beet	Sugar production	Leaves and tops
Rice	Rice production	Straw
Olives	Oil production	Pits
Olives	Olive and oil production	Pruning
Citrus	Citrus production	Pruning
Grape	Wine production	Pruning

Table 1: Agricultural residues

153 Wind and solar power have been deeply investigated by several authors and within numerous projects,
154 due to their acknowledged relevance in renewable energy production [34].

155 Among them, the Global Wind Atlas [35, 11] contains data on wind power density for 50, 100 and 200 m
156 high hubs with a spatial resolution of 1km x 1km. Data on solar radiation were retrieved from the PVGIS
157 project [36, 37]. Specifically we used data on the global solar radiation on optimally inclined surfaces.

158 Among the selected renewable sources, we decided to include the municipal solid waste, due to the role
159 waste currently plays in energy extraction [34]. Specifically, we included only the non recyclable share
160 of urban waste, which may be used in digestion processes for energy extraction. The data on municipal
161 solid waste from households and economic activities (Statistical Classification of Economic Activities in the
162 European Community [38]) were collected from the Eurostat Database for the year 2014.

163 Table 2 refers to the current data availability for these main energy sources among the previously cited
164 projects. All collected data do not include technical aspects in the assessment of the energy potential (e.g.
165 efficiency, energy losses, etc.).

166 2.2. Harmonization of energy potential indicators at NUTS3 level

167 First, in order to identify spatial patterns considering an homogeneous administrative unit, existing data
168 on energy potential, see table 2, were down-scaled at NUTS3 level. Secondly, we considered similar criteria
169 into the definition of energy potential. Generally, we tried to include sustainable criteria and above all to
170 reduce conflicts with competing uses of the natural resource. Both elaborations were carried out by inte-
171 grating GIS data into the original energy-potential dataset.

172
173 The data related to biomass already account for sustainable criteria but they refer to each country. They
174 were down-scaled at NUTS3 level by means of GIS. Data on the energy potential of agricultural biomass

Energy potential	Data source	Spatial resolution	Potential definition
Agricultural residues P_{agr}	Intelligent Energy Europe [30]	NUTS0	Sustainable criteria
Forest residues P_{for}	Intelligent Energy Europe [30]	NUTS0	Sustainable criteria
Livestock residues P_{liv}	Intelligent Energy Europe [30]	NUTS0	Sustainable criteria
Municipal solid waste per person P_{mun}	Intelligent Energy Europe [30]	NUTS0	Sustainable criteria
Waste water treatment plant P_{ww}	Hotmaps Project [22]	Plant position	Sustainable criteria
Wind P_{wind}	DTU Global Atlas [35]	1km x 1km	Theoretical potential
Solar power P_{sun}	PVgis [36]	1km x 1km	Theoretical potential

Table 2: Data source and spatial resolution of energy potential indicators

175 were computed at NUTS3 level by using the LUCAS framework [39], a survey that provides statistics on
176 land use and cover in the EU28 territory. The LUCAS grid was re-elaborated to extract only the land cover
177 classes relevant to our research, i.e. those relative to the selected biomasses, for each NUTS3 unit.

178 Data on the energy potential of livestock effluents were redistributed at NUTS3 level using the Eurostat
179 statistics on the number of manure storage facilities in each province as proxy.

180 Forest biomass here includes two categories of residues originated from forest management, namely,
181 fuel wood and residues from fuel wood and round wood. Data on energy potential at NUTS 0 level were
182 elaborated and unified to compute the total energy potential of forest biomass at national level. For the
183 spatialization of these data at NUTS3 level, the Corine Land Cover framework was used.

184 In order to obtain an indicator of energy potential that is not depending on the size of the territorial
185 units, the final values for all biomass sources were divided by the area of the NUTS3 unit.

186

The potential of municipal solid waste from household and economic activities at national level was
computed by using a lower heating value (l_h) of 13,8 MJ Kg⁻¹ and an equivalence ratio (r) of 0,3 [40],
according to the following formula:

$$\hat{P}_{mun} = Q_{mun} \cdot l_h \cdot r$$

187 \hat{P}_{mun} indicates the potential from MSW, while Q_{mun} indicates the quantity. The 2011 Census from the Eu-
188 rostat Database [23] was used as proxy to spatialize the potential of household waste at NUTS3 level. The
189 potential of waste from economic activities at NUTS3 level was obtained by using the 2014 GDP statistics
190 from the Eurostat Database as proxy since the GDP is an indicator of the economic performance of a region,
191 hence of the performance and status of a region's economic activities.

192

193 For what concerns the potential from waste water treatment plants, solar and wind power the potentials
194 were aggregated at NUTS3 level starting from data with an higher resolution. Again, in computing the
195 potential, we followed sustainable criteria, in order to obtain a realistic measure of the availability of the
196 resources.

197 Specifically, to calculate the water treatment plant potential, according to [29], we summed up the power
198 of all suitable plant within the borders of each NUTS3. The extraction of energy from these plants should be
199 economically feasible since are close to infrastructures. Similarly to what we did for municipal solid waste,
200 we divided the energy potential by the population of each NUTS3 area, in order to get a specific indicator
201 for each territorial unit.

202 The wind potential at NUTS3 level was estimated by following these sustainability criteria [41]:

- 203 • Inclusion of low or sparse vegetation, bare and burnt areas only (from the Corine Land Cover)
- 204 • Exclusion of 1 km buffer areas containing cities and settlements (extracted from the Corine Land
205 Cover)
- 206 • Exclusion of area above 2500 m.a.s.l.
- 207 • Exclusion of corridors for bird connectivity (Common Database on Designated Areas, CDDA)
- 208 • Exclusion of protected areas of the Natura2000 network

209 The estimation of wind potential here considered is the annual median value considering a distance among
210 wind hubs of 300 m, for each NUTS3 area.

211 In order to estimate a feasible solar energy potential, the calculations were made supposing to install
212 solar panels only on building roofs: the European Settlement Map, downloaded from the Copernicus Land
213 Monitoring System [24], served as building footprint. The estimation of solar potential here considered is
214 the annual median value for each NUTS3 area. Table 3 summarizes the selected and harmonized energy
215 potentials indicators.

216 2.3. Non-energy territorial indicators

217 The exploitation of the potential from renewable sources strictly depends on specific territorial aspects.
218 del Río and Burguillo [42] highlight how renewable energy production impacts on local development,
219 above all in rural area, by creating industries and employment opportunities. Belmonte et al. [43] stress the
220 importance of connections between energy potential and socio-environmental conditions for the creation of
221 energy related territorial plans. For this reasons, it seemed essential to include some sort of indicator about
222 the spatial location, geographic features and economic and sociodemographic structure of the territorial
223 units. Since the aim of this study is the classification of energy potential, we refer only to existing datasets.

Variable	Measure	Unit of measure
\hat{P}_{agr}	Potential of agricultural residues per km ²	PJ km ⁻²
\hat{P}_{for}	Potential of forest residues per km ²	PJ km ⁻²
\hat{P}_{liv}	Potential of livestock residues per km ²	PJ km ⁻²
\hat{P}_{mun}	Potential of municipal solid waste per person	PJ inhab ⁻¹
\hat{P}_{ww}	Potential of waste water per person	KW inhab ⁻¹
\hat{P}_{wind}	Potential of wind at 100 meters	GWh hub ⁻¹
\hat{P}_{sun}	Potential of solar power	kWh m ⁻²

Table 3: Energy potential indicators at NUTS3 level

224 Universally acknowledged indicators, like surface area, population and GDP were then considered and
225 additional socio-economic variables were selected based on studies on the assessment of territorial cohesion.
226 We also included electricity and gas prices and data on heating and cooling degree days in order to represent
227 the energy consumption of the territories: Quayle and Diaz [44] showed a very high correlation between
228 energy consumption and heating degree days. Starting from the monthly average of heating and cooling
229 degree days, we computed the annual data. The resulting indicators provided information about the need of
230 a territory for heating and cooling and allowed to perform a more accurate energy-potential classification.

231 Most indicators were collected from the Eurostat database and re-elaborated at NUTS3 level when
232 necessary (see Table 4 for details).

233 The indicator representing the percentage of urban area at NUTS3 level was obtained by extracting from
234 the Corine Land Cover the classes related to urban areas and by calculating the percentage of those areas
235 on the total surface in each NUTS3 area.

236 The indicator measuring elevation is based on EU-DEM, a digital surface model by Copernicus Land
237 Monitoring Service [45]. The measure for elevation was already available at NUTS3.

238 The final draft of variables according to which the territorial units are clustered are summarized in table
239 4.

240 3. A cluster analysis to classify territories based on renewable energy potential

241 Cluster analysis encompasses different mathematical methods to group objects according to similarities:
242 objects characterized by similar features are gathered in the same cluster according to a given algorithm [46].
243 Besides merely classifying a number of objects, cluster analysis offers interesting cues for testing research
244 hypotheses [46].

There are different variations of cluster analysis: the one used in this study is the k-means, a non-hierarchical clusterization method. This method selects k objects to use as cluster seeds, and then distributes

Indicator	Description	Unit of measure
<i>lat</i>	Latitude of centroid	deg
<i>long</i>	Longitude of centroid	deg
<i>A</i>	Surface area	km ²
<i>/rho_{pop}</i>	Population density	inhab km ⁻²
<i>N_{pop}</i>	Population	-
<i>A_{pop}</i>	Urban areas	%
<i>gdp</i>	GDP	€
<i>p_{el}</i>	Electricity price *	€ kWh ⁻¹
<i>p_{gas}</i>	Gas price *	€ kWh ⁻¹
<i>N_{edu}</i>	Inhabitants with tertiary education **	%
<i>N_{unemp}</i>	Percentage of unemployed people between 20 and 64 **	%
<i>income</i>	Disposable income of private households per capita **	€ inhab ⁻¹
<i>gdp_{pps}</i>	Gross Domestic Product in Purchasing Power Standard per person **	€ inhab ⁻¹
<i>r&d</i>	Research and Development expenditure per capita **	€ inhab ⁻¹
<i>h</i>	Surface elevation **	m a.s.l.
<i>hdd</i>	Annual heating degree days **	K d ⁻¹
<i>cdd</i>	Annual cooling degree days **	K d ⁻¹

Table 4: Non-energy related territorial indicators * at NUTS0 level and ** at NUTS2 level.

the remaining objects to the clusters. The distribution into clusters is based on the Euclidean distance between every two objects: the following formula defines this distance.

$$d(x, y) = \left(\sum_{j=1}^d (x_j - y_j)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

245 The cluster seeds are chosen in order to have a large Euclidean distance between them while the distribution
246 of the remaining objects is done by keeping the Euclidean distance within the same cluster as small as
247 possible [46].

248 The first step in cluster analysis is the selection of the variables [47]. This step is particularly delicate
249 since, as Kaufman and Rousseeuw [48] stated, in cluster analysis, a variable not containing any relevant
250 information is worse than useless, because it will make the clustering less apparent. The occurrence of
251 so-called trash variables has the potential to cripple the whole clustering process because they yield a lot of
252 random terms in distances, thereby hiding the useful information provided by the other variables [47]. All
253 variables thus contribute equally to define the cluster structure.

254 We directly selected a subset of initial variables accounting for energy potential assessment since the aim
255 of this work is to identify energy related spatial patterns. Once data relative to all selected variables were
256 collected or re-elaborated at NUTS3 level, the cluster analysis was carried out in R [49].

257 The database containing observations related to each EU28 NUTS3 area was re-organized and the pres-
258 ence of missing data was checked. Variables presenting more than 18% of missing values were excluded
259 from the analysis. In variables presenting missing values below 18% of the total, these were replaced by the
260 mean value for that variable. A second test checked the presence of correlation between the variables: a
261 correlation greater than the absolute value of 0.85 was tested.

262 In order to perform cluster analysis, and specifically the k-means algorithm, data needed to be stan-
263 dardized. This step was necessary since each variable ranges over a different scale, with different orders of
264 magnitude.

265 Once the data were on the same scale for all variables, the presence of natural clusters in the dataset,
266 i.e. the tendency of the data to group, was tested.

267 First, we checked the cluster tendency in the distribution of the data by linear multidimensionality
268 reduction: through the t-distributed stochastic neighbor embedding (t-SNE) algorithm, it was possible to
269 represent a multi-variable dataset in two dimensions, as shown by the scatter plot in Figure 1. Each color
270 is intended to represent a possible cluster. t-SNE is not an exact method of identifying the optimal number
271 of clusters present in a dataset, though the number of colors present in the plot can already give a rough
272 estimation of it.

273 The second tool used to estimate the number of clusters possibly present in the data was NbClust [50].

Figure 1: t-SNE plot

274 This algorithm uses 30 indices for determining the best number of clusters, by also giving the user the
 275 possibility to choose three key arguments

- 276 • the measure of the distance used to compute the dissimilarity matrix
- 277 • the minimum and the maximum number of clusters
- 278 • the cluster analysis method

279 In this case, the distance measure employed was Euclidean, the minimum and maximum number of clusters
280 were set respectively at 15 and 20 and the method chosen was k-means. With these arguments, the number
281 of clusters proposed by the highest number of indices was 17.

282 The last test used to confirm the tendency of the data to group in a defined number of clusters was
283 the Hopkins statistic [51]. The result of the Hopkins statistic is a number from zero to 1: the closer the
284 number to zero, the higher the tendency of the data to cluster; with values far below 0.5, the dataset is
285 significantly clusterable. The Hopkins statistic with 17 clusters gave a result of $6.95 \cdot 10^{-2}$, confirming a
286 significant tendency of the data to group into 17 clusters.

287 After confirming the cluster tendency and having possibly found the best number of clusters for the
288 dataset, the k-means algorithm was applied to the data. This algorithm clusters the data matrix, in this
289 case the scaled dataset, according to a given number of clusters (17), a maximum number of iterations (50),
290 and a number of random starts (multiple random starts are recommended, we used 10), and finally returns:

- 291 • the number of elements comprised in each cluster
- 292 • the centroid of each cluster for all variables
- 293 • a vector pairing each observation with the cluster it belongs to
- 294 • the variance between the clusters over the total variance in the data

295 The last information is particularly relevant: it indicates how much the variance in the dataset is explained
296 by the clustering. The higher this percentage, the more significant the clustering of the data based on the
297 selected variables: in this case, it assumed the value of 61,3%.

298 4. Results and discussion

299 The k-means algorithm grouped the NUTS3 territories of EU28 and Switzerland into 17 clusters. Each
300 cluster is characterized by a centroid, representing the mean value for all elements of the cluster for each
301 variables. Figure 2 plots the centroids of each cluster by highlighting the correlation among indicators
302 through dendrograms.

303 4.1. Classification of territories based on renewable energy potential

304 The classification of territories is better visualized through the map in Figure 3. Each cluster has
305 been analyzed based on the value of all indicators in its centroid. The quantitative values assumed by
306 the indicators in the centroid have been converted into qualitative assessments, so that in the centroid of
307 each cluster, the indicator can assume one of the following values: very high, high, medium/high, medium,
308 medium/low, low, very low.

Figure 2: Centroids analysis with dendrogram

309 Below are listed the most relevant cluster in terms of renewable energy potential, i.e. the ones presenting
 310 very high or high values for at least one indicator relative to renewable energy potential. For each cluster,
 311 the other renewable source or sources with a high potential indicator are mentioned, along with the values
 312 assumed by other indicators, when significant.

313 Examples of territories comprised in each cluster are given.

314 Clusters 2, 9, 12, 13 and 17 are not mentioned due to their low renewable energy potentials.

315 Cluster 1 - Alpine areas with very high potential from waste water per person This cluster includes
 316 the Alpine area, encompassing the southern part of Austria, four departments of southeastern France, six
 317 provinces of northern Italy and the best part of Switzerland. From an energy point of view, the elements
 318 of this cluster present also a medium/high potential from forest biomass, a medium/high potential from
 319 municipal solid waste per person and a medium potential from wind. The elevation of the territories in this

Figure 3: Clusters in the EU28 and Switzerland

320 area is very high, consequently the heating demand assumes very high values whilst the cooling demand
 321 assume very low values. For what concerns socioeconomic indicators, the unemployment rate is very low
 322 and so is GDP in PPS per person.

323 Cluster 3 - Highly urbanized areas with very high potential from municipal solid waste per person This
 324 cluster includes the metropolitan boroughs of the inner area of London (UK), the city of Paris (France)

325 and two other departments of the Ile-de-France, the arrondissement (district) of Bruxelles (BE) and the
326 Romanian capital of Bucharest. From an energy point of view, the elements of this cluster also present
327 a medium/high potential from waste water per person. The heating demand is medium/high. For what
328 concerns socioeconomic indicators, population density and concentration of urbanized areas are very high,
329 the unemployment rate is low, income per capita and GDP in PPS per capita are both very high. As for
330 education and research, these areas show a very high percentage of people with tertiary education.

331 Cluster 4 - Innovation oriented areas with high potential from forest biomass per m² and high potential
332 from waste water treatment plants per person This cluster includes mostly German territories, like the
333 Landkreis of Dachau; it also comprises the arrondissement of Nivelles (Belgium), the region of North Zealand
334 and the island of Bornholm (Denmark), the state of Luxembourg and three districts of the Bundesland of
335 Styria (Austria). From an energy point of view, the elements of this cluster present also a medium/high
336 potential from municipal solid waste per person Electricity prices are very high and the heating demand
337 is high. For what concerns the socioeconomic indicators, the unemployment rate is very low and income
338 per capita is high. This is the only cluster where the expenditure for research and development per capita
339 assumes very high values.

340 Cluster 5 - North Atlantic areas with very high potential from wind energy This cluster includes mostly
341 territories from the UK and Ireland, like the counties of Durham (UK) and Kerry (Ireland); it also comprises
342 five territories in northern Germany, the Åland Islands in Finland, the French department of Manche and
343 nine territories in the northern Netherlands. From an energy point of view, the elements of this cluster
344 present also a medium/high potential from municipal solid waste per person. The heating demand is high.
345 For what concerns the socioeconomic indicators, GDP in PPS per person is low, while the unemployment
346 rate is very low.

347 Cluster 6 - South Atlantic areas with very high potential from forest biomass per m² and high potential
348 from solar energy This cluster includes the best part of Portugal and the French overseas departments of
349 Guyane, Guadeloupe and Martinique. From an energy point of view, the elements of this cluster present
350 high gas prices. For what concerns the socioeconomic indicators, GDP in PPS per person is very low and
351 income per capita is low. As for education and research, these areas show a very low percentage of people
352 with a tertiary education and a very low expenditure in research and development per capita.

353 Cluster 7 - Mountain areas with high potential from municipal solid waste per person This cluster
354 includes the northern region of Spain including the territories of the Pyrenees, several southern mountainous
355 regions of France including the island of Corsica, the Canary Islands (Spain), the intermunicipal communities
356 of Cávado and Alto Minho and the archipelago of Madeira (Portugal), and two provinces of central Italy.

357 From an energy point of view, the elements of this cluster present a medium/high value for solar energy
358 potential and suffer high gas prices. For what concerns the socioeconomic indicators, GDP in PPS per
359 capita is low.

360 Cluster 8 - Highly populated areas with high potential from municipal solid waste per capita This cluster
361 includes capital cities and highly populated urban areas of Europe: the city of Lisbon (Portugal), the cities
362 of Madrid and Barcelona (Spain), the cities of Rome, Milan, Turin and Naples (Italy), the departments of
363 Bouches-du-Rhône, with the city of Marseille, Rhône-Alpes, with the city of Lyon, and Nord, with the city
364 of Lille (France), the city of Dublin (Ireland), the city of Amsterdam (Netherlands), the cities of Berlin,
365 Hamburg and Munich (Germany), the city of Wien (Austria), the city of Stockholms (Sweden) and the city
366 of Helsinki (Finland). From an energy point of view, the elements of this cluster suffer a high price for gas.
367 For what concerns the socioeconomic indicators, population and GDP of these areas are very high.

368 Cluster 10 - North Atlantic areas with a very high potential from livestock effluents per m² and high po-
369 tential for municipal solid waste per person This cluster includes territories commonly known for livestock
370 breeding: the best part of the Netherlands, the West Flanders territories in Belgium, two Swiss cantons and
371 three departments in the French region of Brittany. For what concerns the socioeconomic indicators, the
372 elements of this cluster present a very low unemployment rate and a low GDP in PPS per capita.

373 Cluster 11 - Central European areas with very high potential from forest biomass per m² and high
374 potential from waste water per person This cluster includes mostly German and Belgian territories, like
375 the Landkreis of Ostallgäu and the arrondissement of Verviers; it also comprises two Swiss cantons and the
376 best part of Slovenia. From an energy point of view, the elements of this cluster suffer very high prices
377 for electricity and present a high heating demand. For what concerns the socioeconomic indicators, GDP
378 in PPS per person is low, while the unemployment rate is very low. As for education and research, the
379 percentage of people with a tertiary education is low and so is the expenditure in research and development
380 per capita.

381 Cluster 14 - West Mediterranean areas with high potential from municipal solid waste per capita and
382 very high potential from solar energy This cluster comprises all territories of southern Italy, including the
383 islands of Sicily and Sardinia, all southern Spain territories, two inter-municipal communities of Portugal
384 and the state of Malta. From an energy point of view, the elements of this cluster present a medium/high
385 potential from waste water and a medium potential from wind energy. They have a very high cooling
386 demand, and suffer very high gas prices. For what concerns the socioeconomic indicators, GDP in PPS is
387 very low and the unemployment rate is high. As for education and research, a very low percentage of people
388 have tertiary education and the expenditure for research and development per capita is very low.

389 Cluster 15 - North Atlantic areas with very high potential from agricultural biomass per m² and high po-
390 tential from waste water per person. This cluster includes territories of north and central Europe commonly
391 known for their agricultural production, encompassing numerous areas of Germany, the French department
392 of Somme, part of the eastern coast of England (UK), the best part of Denmark, ten Belgian territories
393 and two regions of northern Austria. The elements of this cluster suffer very high prices for electricity and
394 present a high heating demand. For what concerns the socioeconomic indicators, the unemployment rate
395 is very low, and GDP in PPS per capita is low. As for education and research, a low percentage of people
396 have tertiary education and the expenditure for research and development per capita is low.

397 Cluster 16 - East Mediterranean areas with high potential from solar energy. This cluster includes all
398 continental territories and islands of Greece and the state of Cyprus. For what concerns the socioeconomic
399 indicators, the elements of this cluster present a very high unemployment rate, a low income per capita, a
400 very low GDP in PPS per capita. As for education and research, a low percentage of people have tertiary
401 education and the expenditure for research and development per capita is very low.

402 4.2. Heterogeneities and common grounds: a comparison between EU macro-regions and clusters

403 As it can be seen in the following maps, the macro regions of EU, often object of energy and non-
404 energy related projects, encompass heterogeneous territories from the point of view of our energy potential
405 classification. It is therefore essential to understand what are the causes for this heterogeneity and what
406 territories have in common beside geographic location, in order to encourage more effective policies.

407 The Adriatic-Ionian region (Figure 4) presents nine clusters inside its boundaries. For what concerns the
408 assessment of renewable energy sources, the territories of this area present a similar potential from municipal
409 solid waste, generally assuming high values, while all other sources present quite diverse potentials. The
410 energy market is very heterogeneous: electricity and gas have very diverse prices according to the country.
411 The potential energy demand, under the hypothesis of being correlated with heating and cooling degree days,
412 assumes very different values, ranging from very low to very high. The economic context also presents some
413 inconsistencies. The unemployment rate is generally low with the exception of cluster 14 and 16, having
414 respectively high and very high levels of unemployment. Income per capita assume very different values
415 while the GDP in PPS per capita is generally low. As for research and education, the territories share both
416 a low percentage of people with tertiary education and a low expenditure for research and development.

417 The Alpine region (Figure 5) presents ten clusters inside its boundaries. For what concerns the assessment
418 of renewable energy sources, the territories of this area present a similar potential from municipal solid
419 waste and from waste water, assuming mainly medium and high values; all other sources though present
420 very diverse potentials. The prices of electricity and gas also assume very different values. Conversely, the
421 heat demand is homogeneous in the area due to the mountain environment covering a considerable share of

Figure 4: Clusters in the Adriatic-Ionian region

422 the territories: the values for heating degree days is generally high, while that for cooling degree day is low.
 423 The economic context is quite consistent among the territories: unemployment is generally low, income per
 424 capita assumes mainly high values while the GDP in PPS per capita is low. As for research and education,
 425 the territories share a low-medium/low percentage of people with tertiary education but the expenditure in
 426 research and development range from very low to very high values.

427 The Baltic region (6) presents eight clusters inside its boundaries. For what concerns the potential
 428 from renewable energy sources, the territories of this area are quite similar, in particular the potential from
 429 municipal solid waste and from waste water is medium/high while the majority of the others are low. There
 430 are though two exceptions: the potentials from forest biomass and wind power both range from very low
 431 to very high values. The prices of electricity and gas assume very different values. Conversely, the heat
 432 demand is very similar in the whole area: heating degree days assume high values while cooling degree days
 433 are generally low, due to the high latitude of the territories. The economic context is quite consistent among
 434 the territories: unemployment is low, income per capita mainly assumes medium/high values and the GDP
 435 in PPS per capita is low. As for research and education, the territories share a low percentage of people
 436 with tertiary education while expenditure in research and development assumes very different values.

Figure 5: Clusters in the Alpine region

437 The Danube region (7) presents ten clusters inside its boundaries. For what concerns the potential from
 438 renewable energy sources, the territories of this area are quite different with the exception of the potentials
 439 from municipal solid waste and waste water, generally high. Conversely, the heat demand is consistent
 440 in the whole area: heating degree days are usually high while cooling degree days are low. The energy
 441 context present heterogeneity regarding the prices of electricity and gas, both ranging from very low to very
 442 high values. The economic context is heterogeneous when it comes to GDP in PPS per capita, instead
 443 unemployment and income are consistent, assuming respectively low and medium/high values. The region
 444 presents pronounced differences in the research and education context: both the percentage of people with
 445 tertiary education and the expenditure in research and development range from very low to very high values.

446
 447 Even though dissimilarities are present in European macro-region, the clusters obtained in this study
 448 highlight similarities among member states that could constitute a base for further EU energy project and
 449 policies. Territories with similar energy potential can lay the groundwork for cooperation, exchange good
 450 practices and policies and encourage renewable energy production.

451 Four examples of clusters with the potential of becoming macro-regions are represented in Figure 8 and

Figure 6: Clusters in the Baltic Sea region

452 listed as follows:

- 453 • The Alps, stretching from Switzerland to Austria, including territories of France and northern Italy
- 454 (cluster 1)
- 455 • The West Mediterranean, encompassing southern Italy and its islands, and the south of Spain with
- 456 the Balearic islands (cluster 14)

Figure 7: Clusters in the Danube region

- 457 • The East European Plain, including Poland, Czech Republic and the Baltic countries (cluster 2)
- 458 • The Carpathians, comprising Bulgaria, Romania, Hungary, Slovakia and Croatia (cluster 17)

459 5. Conclusions and policy recommendations

460 The analysis here performed lays the foundations for a comprehensive territorial classification of the
 461 EU28 area and Switzerland, one that includes details on the energy profile, the geomorphological character-
 462 ization and the socio-economic structure of the territories. Two key aspects are stressed by means of this
 463 classification:

- 464 • the study area is very heterogeneous: two territories located in the same country or geographical region
 465 can present substantial differences in energy and non-energy related aspects; they thus face different
 466 challenges and issues when it comes to renewable energy production and consequently require different
 467 policy approaches
- 468 • although heterogeneous, the study area presents interesting spatial patterns: two territories sharing
 469 neither national identity nor similar geographic coordinates can have a lot in common; from an energy

Figure 8: New macro-regions

470 perspective they can hold comparable sources or be subject to the same energy prices, as for the non-
 471 energy layout, they could have developed similar economic environments or be interested by analogous
 472 social phenomena.

473 The inclusion in the analysis of both energy and non-energy related indicators provides a new perspective on
 474 how to approach cross-country policies and programmes. Specifically, two types of policy recommendation
 475 arise from these results. At macro level, this classification can be used by EU decision makers for designing
 476 more focused energy policies. The scope of macro-regional policies could be adjusted according to the
 477 clusters resulting from this study, in order to obtain tailor-made and territory oriented measures.

478 For instance, clusters 1, 7 and 10 are the core of the Alpine macro-region (Figure 5); these clusters are
 479 in fact statistically "close" when looking at the dendrogram distribution in Figure 2, meaning they behave
 480 similarly with respect to relevant indicators. From an energy perspective, the potential from municipal solid
 481 waste, electricity and gas prices assume similar values; unemployment is generally low, income per capita
 482 is medium and GDP in PPS per capita is low in all three clusters. Nevertheless, other indicators assume

483 very different values and projects should focus on leveling out these differences in order to use territorial
484 cohesion as a mean for promoting renewable energy production.

485 At micro level, local administrators and energy managers can use these results as an energy planning tool,
486 by comparing their experience with that of other territories belonging to the same cluster and formulating
487 energy related plans accordingly. The territories of a cluster could exchange ideas and good practices among
488 each other, try out successful strategies, and avoid unsuccessful ones, ipso facto facilitating decision making
489 and turning energy planning into a bottom-up process.

490 For instance, all cities comprised in cluster 8 share a high potential from municipal solid waste, though
491 some managed to put in place more successful strategies for producing energy from this renewable source,
492 than others. The exchange of knowledge and information could be key in spreading effective measures in
493 this sense, in all territories of the cluster.

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500 7. References

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